

IL28B polymorphisms in patients with HBeAg negative chronic HBV infection genotype D

Emilia Hadziyannis¹, Andreas Laras¹, Eleni Panopoulou¹, Alexandros Gryparis²,
Stephanos J. Hadziyannis¹

¹Academic Department of Medicine at Hippokration Hospital, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens Greece,

²Department of Hygiene, Epidemiology and Medical Statistics, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens Greece.

Summary

Aim of the study: Evaluation of possible associations of single nucleotide polymorphisms upstream the interferon-lambda 3 (IL28B) gene with the phases of HBeAg-negative chronic hepatitis B virus (HBV) genotype D infection and with patient outcomes in a Caucasian population.

Materials and methodology: The IL-28B rs12979860 polymorphisms were evaluated in 400 Greek patients with HBeAg-negative chronic HBV infection genotype D (n=311 with chronic hepatitis B, n=89 inactive HBsAg carriers) and a control group of 222 healthy adults of the same race and ethnicity. Associations with the phase of the infection, response to interferon and/or nucleos(t)ide analogue (NA) therapy, development of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and spontaneous HBsAg clearance were investigated.

Results: The distribution of IL28B genotypes and C and T allele frequency among the overall cohort

of patients with chronic HBV infection was not statistically different from the general population. In males inactive HBsAg carriers the CC genotype (59%) and C allele (74.5%) were statistically significantly more prevalent compared to chronic hepatitis B patients (37.7%, $p=0.028$ and 59.5%, $p=0.005$, respectively) and the general population (31.4%, $p=0.018$ and 58%, $p=0.005$, respectively). There was no association between IL28B polymorphisms and allele frequencies with spontaneous HBsAg clearance, response to treatment or development of HCC.

Conclusions: IL28B polymorphisms at rs12979860 alone do not appear to play any role in the spontaneous or treatment related outcomes of HBeAg-negative genotype D infection in Caucasians, but the possibility that CC genotype and C allele favor the development of the inactive HBsAg carrier state in males should be further investigated.

Key words

genotype D, HBV, IL28B, natural history, treatment

Corresponding author

Emilia Hadziyannis,
63-67 Evrou str., 115 27 Athens, Greece
Tel: +30 213 2088603
Fax +30 213 2088601
email address: emhadzi@med.uoa.gr

Introduction

Common single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) upstream the interferon (IFN)-lambda 3 gene (IL28B) on chromosome 19, have been well documented to be associated with HCV RNA clearance in patients with untreated acute HCV infection and with a favorable response of chronic hepatitis C (CHC) to treatment with pegylated interferon (peg IFN).¹⁻⁴ Initial studies looking for similar associations in HBV infection have yielded some positive results regarding the response to IFN treatment but in subsequent reports an overall link between IL28B polymorphisms and sustained response to IFN-treatment could not be confirmed, both in HBeAg-positive and HBeAg-negative chronic hepatitis B (CHB) patients.⁵⁻¹¹ Additionally, the possibility for an association with spontaneous HBV DNA clearance and HBsAg loss has also started to be investigated.^{12,13} However, current data are limited, controversial and mainly on Asian patients.^{7,11,14-17} These discrepancies have been stressed in editorials and systematic review articles.¹⁸⁻²¹ Several reasons have been considered to account for contrasting findings in retrospective studies such as differences in treatment regimens and their duration, differences in study end points, heterogeneity in follow-up data as well as differences in ethnic backgrounds and in HBV genotypes.^{20,22,23} On the basis of hitherto data, it is pointed out that IL28B polymorphisms may have only a limited, if any, role on the response to IFN treatment

of HBeAg-negative CHB, probably restricted only to patients with HBeAg-negative genotype D infection, while an effect on the natural course and final outcome of CHB still remains unknown.^{15,16,20,24,25} Moreover, there are no data on IL28B polymorphism in the inactive HBsAg carrier state and in relation to its long term outcome.

In view of these conjectures, we conducted the present study on the IL28B polymorphism at rs12979860 and the frequency of the C and T alleles in a large population of Caucasian patients in Greece, with HBeAg-negative CHB infection genotype D, in comparison with the general population of the same ethnicity. We also aimed to evaluate the incidence of the rs12979860 polymorphism and of its alleles in the 2 main phases of the natural course of HBeAg negative CHB infection, including a sizeable group of inactive HBsAg carriers. In patients with active chronic HBV infection we looked for possible association of the "favorable" CC genotype with sustained responses to IFN as well as to nucleos(t)ide analogue (NA) therapy; and evaluated the influence of this genetic factor in patients who developed hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC).

Materials and Methods

Patients: A total of 400 Greek subjects with HBeAg-negative HBV infection were included in the study. The results were compared overall, by group and by

gender with the frequencies of IL28B genotypes at rs12979860 and of C and T alleles of a control group of 222 healthy adults of the same race and ethnicity. A group of 221 patients had received treatment with IFN and/or NAs.

All patients had been followed-up prospectively on clinical grounds and by frequent laboratory testing from 1990 to 2012 at the Liver Unit and Molecular Biology Laboratory of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens and have given informed consent for research use of their biological samples. The patients were classified in the following subgroups:

1. CHB treated with IFN (conventional or pegylated) at least for one year (n= 84)
2. CHB patients treatment naïve (n=137) or previous non-responders to IFN therapy (n=38) subjected to long-term treatment with various NAs without development of resistant to the applied NAs, HBV variants (total n=175).
3. Inactive HBsAg carriers (n=89) with and without spontaneous HBsAg loss during the long term follow up period.
4. CHB patients (treated and untreated) who developed HCC (n=38).

Methods: Blood samples or sera stored at -70° C were assessed for the rs12979860 genotypes (CC, CT or TT) and for the prevalence of the C and T alleles in the IL-28B locus. Genomic DNA was purified using the High Pure PCR Template Preparation Kit (Roche, Mannheim, Germany). Genotype analysis of the IL-28B promoter polymorphism at position -3176C/T (rs12979860) was performed with a commercially available genotyping assay (LightMix Kit IL28B, Cat.-No. 40-0588-32 TIB MOLBIOL, Berlin, Germany) by

melting curve analysis of real-time PCR amplification products using the Light Cycler instrument (Roche Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Statistical Analysis: Allele and genotype frequencies were calculated according to the Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium Theory. Categorical variables are presented as frequencies. To investigate relationships between categorical variables Pearson's chi-square was used. All reported p-values are based on two-sided tests and significance level was set to 5%. IBM SPSS Statistics 21 software was used for all the statistical calculations.

Results

Prevalence of IL28B polymorphisms in HBeAg negative HBV infection and the general population

The prevalence of the IL28B genotypes at rs12979860 and of the C and T alleles in the patients with chronic HBV infection and in the general population is depicted in table 1. In the general population (n=222) genotypes CC, CT and TT were observed in 78 (35.1%), 113 (50.9%) and 31 (14%) individuals, respectively. In chronic HBV infection (n=400) genotypes CC, CT and TT were found in 153 (38.2%), 187 (46.7%) and 60 (15%) patients, respectively. The frequency of the C allele was 60.5% for the general population and 61.6% for patients with chronic HBV infection. No significant differences were found in the IL28B genotypes or the allele frequencies between patients with chronic HBeAg negative HBV infection and the general healthy population.

Table 1 IL28B genotype and allele frequency in the general population and in patients with chronic HBV infection

IL28B GENOTYPE	GENERAL POPULATION			CHRONIC HBV INFECTION		
	TOTAL (n=222)	MALES (n=102)	FEMALES (n=120)	TOTAL (n=400)	MALES (n=309)	FEMALES (n=129)
CC	35.1%	31.4%	38.3%	38.2%	41.5%	30.5%
CT	50.9%	53.9%	48.3%	46.75%	41.5%	59.3%
TT	14.0%	14.7%	13.3%	15.0%	17.0%	10.2%
IL28B ALLELE						
C	60.5%	58%	62.5%	61.6%	62.3%	60.2%
T	39.5%	42%	37.5%	38.4%	37.8%	39.8%

Table 2 IL28B genotype and allele frequency in the two main subsets of patients with chronic HBeAg-negative HBV infection

IL28B GENOTYPE	INACTIVE CARRIERS			CHRONIC ACTIVE INFECTION		
	TOTAL (n=89)	MALES (n=51)	FEMALES (n=38)	TOTAL (n=311)	MALES (n=231)	FEMALES (n=80)
CC	46%	59%*	29%	36.0%	37.7%	31.3%
CT	44%	31%	60.5%	47.6%	43.7%	58.7%
TT	10%	10%	10.5%	16.4%	18.6%	10.0%
IL28B ALLELE						
C	68%	74.5%**	59%	59.8%	59.5%	60.6%
T	32%	25.5%	41%	40.2%	40.5%	39.4%

* $p=0.005$, ** $p=0.028$

Prevalence in different subgroups of chronic HBV infection

The distributions of the IL28B genotypes at rs12979860 and of the C and T alleles did not differ statistically between inactive HBV carriers (n=89) and patients with chronic active HBeAg negative infection (n=311). Genotype CC was found in 41 (46%), CT in 39 (44%) and TT in 9 (10%) of the inactive HBsAg carriers and 112 (36%), 148 (47.6%) and 51 (16.4%) of patients with chronic active hepatitis B, respectively. When the results were analyzed by sex it was demonstrated that male inactive HBsAg carriers had significantly higher prevalence ($p=0.005$) of the C allele with a frequency of 74.5% and the CC genotype ($p=0.028$) with a prevalence of 59% compared to males with chronic active hepatitis B (C allele 59.5%, CC genotype 37.7%) (Table 2), as well as compared to the male general population (C allele 58% - $p=0.005$, CC genotype 31.4% - $p=0.018$).

No statistically significant difference was seen either in IL28B genotype ($p=0.618$) or in the allele prevalence ($p=0.423$) between inactive carriers with and without spontaneous HBsAg loss (Table 3). The rs12979860 C allele frequency was 64.5% and 71 %, respectively. Inactive HBsAg carriers with spontaneous HBsAg clearance were statistically significantly older by a mean of 8 years ($p=0.0046$, 95% confidence intervals: 2.55-13.52) than those who did not clear HBsAg.

Additionally, no predominance of the C allele at IL28B rs12979860 was found among patients with treatment related HBsAg loss either after interferon or NA administration (figure 1).

Chronic HBV patients with HCC at presentation or

development during follow up (n=38) did not demonstrate statistical significant difference in the frequency of IL28B genotypes ($p=0.197$) or of C and T alleles ($p=0.695$) compared to the other groups of patients with chronic HBV infection or the general population. Genotype CC found in 46%, CT in 34% and CT in 20% of HCC patients with C allele frequency 63%.

Table 3 IL28B genotype and allele frequency in inactive carrier according to HBSAG clearance during long term follow up.

IL28B GENOTYPE	INACTIVE CARRIERS		
	TOTAL (n=89)	HBsAg Loss(n=44)	No HBsAg loss (n=45)
CC	46%		49%
CT	44%		44.5%
TT	10%		6.5%
IL28B ALLELE			
C	68%	64.5%	71%
T	32%	35.5%	29%

Discussion

This is the first large scale study examining the prevalence of IL28B polymorphisms in Caucasian patients with HBeAg negative chronic HBV infection (genotype D) compared to the general population and its potential role in disease outcomes such as the development of CHB, HBsAg loss and HCC.

The results of this study did not reveal any significant differences in the frequency of IL28B polymorphisms

Figure 1 No predominance of the CC genotype (A) or the C allele (B) at IL28B rs12979860 was found among patients with treatment related HBsAg loss either after interferon or NA administration.

between HBV infected patients and the general population or between the different subsets of HBV patients (CHB, inactive carriers, patients with spontaneous or treatment induced HBsAg loss, HCC). Only male inactive HBsAg carriers were found to have an increased frequency of the CC genotype and C allele compared to CHB patients and the general population.

The observed association of IL28B polymorphisms in males with inactive chronic HBV infection genotype D is rather unexpected and stands in contrast to our negative overall findings and particularly with the absence of a link between IL28B polymorphisms and HBsAg loss. In our population of HBeAg-negative CHB genotype D patients we did not find any correlation between rs12979860 alleles and HBsAg clearance neither in the natural course of the infection nor induced by IFN treatment or long term NA therapy.^{26,27} In support of the finding of higher incidence of CC rs12979860 genotype in inactive male HBV carriers is the observation in Saudi Arabian patients of higher prevalence of the C rs12979860 allele in inactive HBV carriers compared to patients with active hepatitis, cirrhosis and HCC.¹⁴ Further studies among inactive HBsAg carriers of both sexes, of various ethnicities,

harboring different HBV genotypes, are needed to confirm or refute the present findings. In this context it is important to define the characteristics of this particular group of patients. All of them had been identified either in previous field studies or in screening programs mostly of volunteer blood donors in Greece and presented without a previous history of treated or untreated active chronic HBV infection. In addition, they had all been ab initio HBeAg-negative/anti-HBe-positive and had persistently normal ALT levels during a long period of follow-up. Their serum HBV DNA levels never exceeded 20,000 copies/mL and the HBsAg titers were below 2,000 IU/mL. Therefore, they were largely consistent with the definition criteria for the inactive HBV carrier state proposed by Brunetto et al.²⁸

In published studies of the role of IFN- λ 3 polymorphisms as a genetic variable in the outcome of HBV infection, contradictory results have been reported. An association between the IFN- λ 3 genotype CT and the T allele at rs12979860 and development of HCC in HBV infection genotype B and C has been reported in Han Chinese population but not in patients from Korea.^{11,29,30} Moreover, in Han Chinese patients, IL28B

rs12979860 TC/TT and rs12980275 GA/GG genotype combinations were found to further increase the rate of development of HCC in HBV infected individuals.^{31,32} In a meta-analysis the IL28B rs8099917 AA genotype was associated with a decreased risk of HCC (OR =0.63) and the rs12979860 CC genotype with an increased risk for developing liver cirrhosis (OR=1.39).³³ In a treatment-naive population with CHB from Taiwan, 4 SNPs of the IL28B gene were studied, and the rs10853728 CC genotype was found to correlate with hepatitis activity in HBeAg negative chronic HBV infection.³⁴ Also, in HBV-related liver transplantation it was found that recipients with rs8099917 G allele had higher ALT and AST levels and higher HBV-related liver damage.³⁵

A significant number of the HBeAg negative CHB patients included in the present study had been subjected to a yearly treatment and retreatment with conventional or pegIFN alfa.^{10,36} In this group of patients, no association was observed between genotype CC and/or the C allele at rs12979860 with a favorable biochemical and virological response to treatment or with treatment related HBsAg clearance. This is in contrast to the reported association of IL28B polymorphisms and HBsAg seroclearance in a similar subset of HBeAg-negative patients from Italy also infected with HBV genotype D who were treated with conventional or peg IFN and were also followed-up for several years post-treatment.⁶ It is interesting that in another study of HBeAg negative CHB patients from Poland, the IL-28B CC genotype at rs12979860 was negatively associated with response to peg IFN

using an HBV DNA cut off of <400 IU/ml combined with ALT <40 IU/L but not with HBVDNA <2,000 IU/ml.³⁷ This stresses the importance for the application of uniform criteria to define response to treatment in order to investigate genetic associations and maybe the strictest and closest to cure outcome of HBsAg loss should be used in future studies. In this study 8% of the patients with CC genotype treated with IFN, achieved HBsAg clearance compared to 33 and 17.6% of those with CT and TT genotype. It is significant to note that in our study one third of the patients were previously included in a large Greek study of HBeAg-negative CHB treated with conventional IFN in which a favorable long term outcome terminating to sustained virological response and HBsAg loss was well documented in approximately 40% of them.³⁸

In conclusion, based on our findings on the frequency of IL28B genotypes and alleles at rs 12979860, in a large number of patients with HBeAg negative chronic HBV infection, who were followed-up for a long period for the safe evaluation of spontaneous and treatment-induced outcomes, it becomes apparent that this particular IL28B polymorphism is not playing an important role in the outcome of HBV infection genotype D, except, perhaps, for the spontaneous development of the inactive HBV infection among males.

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Περίληψη

IL28B πολυμορφισμοί σε ασθενείς με HBeAg αρνητική χρόνια HBV λοίμωξη γονοτύπου D

Αιμιλία Χατζηγιάννη¹, Ανδρέας Λαράς¹, Ελένη Πανοπούλου¹, Αλέξανδρος Γρυπάρης²,
Στέφανος Χατζηγιάννης¹

¹Ιπποκράτειο Νοσοκομείο, Β' Πανεπιστημιακή Παθολογική Κλινική και Ομώνυμο Εργαστήριο, Εθνικό και Καποδιστριακό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών, Αθήνα

²Εργαστήριο Υγιεινής, Επιδημιολογίας και Ιατρικής Στατιστικής, Εθνικό και Καποδιστριακό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών, Αθήνα

Στόχος της μελέτης: Η διερεύνηση πιθανών συσχετισμών μεταξύ του πολυμορφισμού C/T, στη θέση -3176 του υποκινητή του γονιδίου της ιντερφερόνης λ3 (IL28B), και του σταδίου της HBeAg αρνητικής χρόνιας λοίμωξης με τον ιό της ηπατίτιδας Β (HBV) γονοτύπου D καθώς και με την έκβαση της νόσου σε Καυκάσιους ασθενείς.

Ασθενείς και μέθοδοι: Ο πολυμορφισμός της IL-28B rs12979860 μελετήθηκε σε 400 Έλληνες ασθενείς με HBeAg αρνητική χρόνια HBV λοίμωξη γονοτύπου D με μακρά κλινική παρακολούθηση, από τους οποίους 311 είχαν χρόνια ηπατίτιδα και οι 89 ήταν ανενεργοί φορείς του ιού. Παράλληλα εξετάσθηκαν 222 υγιείς μάρτυρες της ίδιας φυλής και εθνικότητας. Διερευνήθηκαν πιθανές συσχετίσεις με το στάδιο της λοίμωξης, την απόκριση σε θεραπεία με ιντερφερόνη και/ή νουκλεοσ(τ)ιδικά ανάλογα, την ανάπτυξη ηπατοκυτταρικού καρκίνου καθώς και με την αυτόματη κάθαρση του αντιγόνου επιφάνειας HBsAg.

Αποτελέσματα: Η κατανομή των IL28B rs12979860 γονοτύπων και η συχνότητα των C και T αλληλίων δεν διέφερε στατιστικά σημαντικά μεταξύ του συνόλου των ασθενών χρόνια HBV λοίμωξη και των υγιών μαρτύρων. Άρρενες ανενεργοί φορείς του ιού βρέθηκε να φέρουν τον γονότυπο CC στο 59% και το C αλληλίο στο 74,5%, ποσοστά στατιστικά σημαντικά υψηλότερα από την αντίστοιχη επίπτωση τόσο σε άρρενες ασθενείς με ενεργό χρόνια ηπατίτιδα Β (CC-37.7%, $p=0.028$ και C αλληλίο 59.5%, $p=0.005$) όσο και στο γενικό πληθυσμό (CC-31.4 %, $p=0.018$ και C αλληλίο 58%, $p=0.005$). Δεν βρέθηκε να υπάρχει συσχέτιση μεταξύ του rs12979860 πολυμορφισμού και την αυτόματη ή μετά από θεραπεία κάθαρση του HBsAg ή με την ανάπτυξη ηπατοκυτταρικού καρκίνου.

Συμπεράσματα: Ο rs12979860 IL28B πολυμορφισμός δεν φαίνεται να αποτελεί ανεξάρτητο παράγοντα της αυτόματης ή μετά από θεραπεία έκβασης της HBeAg αρνητικής χρόνιας λοίμωξης με τον ιό της ηπατίτιδας Β (HBV) γονοτύπου D, σε Καυκάσιους ασθενείς. Η πιθανότητα ο CC γονότυπος και το C αλληλίο να ευνοούν την εγκατάσταση του σταδίου της ανενεργού φορίας του ιού σε άρρενες, χρήζει περαιτέρω διερεύνησης.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

γονότυπος D, HBV, IL28B, φυσική πορεία, θεραπεία

References

1. Thomas DL, Thio CL, Martin MP, Qi Y, Ge D, O'Huigin C, et al. Genetic variation in IL28B and spontaneous clearance of hepatitis C virus. *Nature* 2009;461(7265):798-801.
2. Ge D, Fellay J, Thompson AJ, Simon JS, Shianna KV, Urban TJ, et al. Genetic variation in IL28B predicts hepatitis C treatment-induced viral clearance. *Nature* 2009;461(7262):399-401.
3. Suppiah V, Moldovan M, Ahlenstiel G, Berg T, Weltman M, Abate ML, et al. IL28B is associated with response to chronic hepatitis C interferon-alpha and ribavirin therapy. *Nat Genet* 2009;41(10):1100-4.
4. Tanaka Y, Nishida N, Sugiyama M, Kurosaki M, Matsura K, Sakamoto N, et al. Genome-wide association of IL28B with response to pegylated interferon-alpha and ribavirin therapy for chronic hepatitis C. *Nat Genet* 2009;41(10):1105-9.
5. Sonneveld MJ, Wong VW, Woltman AM, Wong GL, Cakaloglu Y, Zeuzem S, et al. Polymorphisms near IL28B and serologic response to peginterferon in HBeAg-positive patients with chronic hepatitis B. *Gastroenterology* 2012;142(3):513-20 e1.
6. Lampertico P, Vigano M, Cheroni C, Facchetti F, Invernizzi F, Valveri V, et al. IL28B polymorphisms predict interferon-related hepatitis B surface antigen seroclearance in genotype D hepatitis B e antigen-negative patients with chronic hepatitis B. *Hepatology* 2013;57(3):890-6.
7. Wu H, Zhao G, Qian F, Liu K, Xie J, Zhou H, et al. Association of IL28B polymorphisms with peginterferon treatment response in Chinese Han patients with HBeAg-positive chronic hepatitis B. *Liver Int* 2014;34(7):1127.
8. Holmes JA, Nguyen T, Ratnam D, Heerasing NM, Tehan JV, Bonanzinga S, et al. IL28B genotype is not useful for predicting treatment outcome in Asian chronic hepatitis B patients treated with pegylated interferon-alpha. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2013;28(5):861-6.
9. Wei L, Wedemeyer H, Liaw YF, et al. No association between IL28B genotype and response to peginterferon alfa-2a (40KD) in HBe antigen-positive and HBe antigen-negative patients with chronic hepatitis B from three large randomized clinical studies. *Hepatology* 2013;58S:686A
10. Hadziyannis SJ, Laras A, Hadziyannis E. Letter: do interferon lambda 3 polymorphisms predict the outcome of interferon therapy in hepatitis B infection? *Aliment Pharmacol Ther* 2014;39(10):1250-1.
11. Lee DH, Cho Y, Seo JY, Kwon JH, Cho EJ, Jang ES, et al. Polymorphisms near interleukin 28B gene are not associated with hepatitis B virus clearance, hepatitis B e antigen clearance and hepatocellular carcinoma occurrence. *Intervirology* 2013;56(2):84-90.
12. Kim SU, Song KJ, Chang HY, Shin EC, Park JY, Kim do Y, et al. Association between IL28B polymorphisms and spontaneous clearance of hepatitis B virus infection. *PloS One* 2013;8(7):e69166.
13. Seto WK, Wong DK, Kopaniszen M, Proitsi P, Sham PC, Hung IF, et al. HLA-DP and IL28B polymorphisms: influence of host genome on hepatitis B surface antigen seroclearance in chronic hepatitis B. *Clin Infect Dis* 2013;56(12):1695-703.
14. Al-Qahtani AA, Al-Anazi MR, Abdo AA, Sanai FM, Al-Hamoudi WK, Alswat KA, et al. Genetic variation in interleukin 28B and correlation with chronic hepatitis B virus infection in Saudi Arabian patients. *Liver Int* 2014; Aug;34(7):e208-16.
15. Jiao XL, Gao YT, Jing L, Liu T, Shi WX, Guo H, et al. [Studies on the relationship between polymorphism of IL-28B rs8099917 and the outcome of HBV infection]. *Zhonghua liu xing bing xue za zhi* 2011;32(11):1143-7.
16. Peng LJ, Guo JS, Zhang Z, Shi H, Wang J, Wang JY. IL28B rs12979860 polymorphism does not influence outcomes of hepatitis B virus infection. *Tissue Antigens* 2012;79(4):302-5.
17. Boglione L, Cusato J, Allegra S, Esposito I, Patti F, Cariti G, et al. Role of IL28-B polymorphisms in the treatment of chronic hepatitis B HBeAg-negative patients with peginterferon. *Antiviral Res* 2014;102:35-43.
18. Stattermayer AF, Scherzer T, Beinhardt S, Rutter K, Hofer H, Ferenci P. Review article: genetic factors that modify the outcome of viral hepatitis. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther* 2014;39(10):1059-70.
19. Galmozzi E, Vigano M, Lampertico P. Systematic review with meta-analysis: do interferon lambda 3 polymorphisms predict the outcome of interferon-therapy in hepatitis B infection? *Aliment Pharmacol Ther* 2014;39(6):569-78. Epub 2014/01/28.
20. Jilg N, Chung RT. One more piece in the interleukin 28B gene puzzle? The case of hepatitis B. *Hepatology* 2013;57(3):870-2.
21. Lee DH, Lee JH, Kim YJ, Park NH, Cho Y, Lee YB, et al. Relationship between polymorphisms near the IL28B gene and spontaneous HBsAg seroclearance: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Viral Hepat* 2014;21(3):163-70.
22. Sonneveld MJ, Brouwer WP, Janssen HL. Studies of IL28B genotype and response to peginterferon in chronic hepatitis B should be stratified by HBV genotype. *Hepatology* 2013;57(3):1283.
23. Stattermayer AF, Ferenci P. Effect of IL28B genotype

- on hepatitis B and C virus infection. *Curr Opin Virol* 14:50-5. 2015(14):5.
24. Martin-Carbonero L, Rallon NI, Benito JM, Poveda E, Gonzalez-Lahoz J, Soriano V. Short communication: Does interleukin-28B single nucleotide polymorphisms influence the natural history of hepatitis B? *AIDS Res Hum Retroviruses* 2012;28(10):1262-4.
 25. Keshvari M, Alavian SM, Sharafi H. How Can the IL28B Polymorphisms with Linkage Disequilibrium Affect the Natural Course of Hepatitis B Inversely? *Liver Int* 2014; 34(7):1127.
 26. Manesis EK, Hadziyannis ES, Angelopoulou OP, Hadziyannis SJ. Prediction of treatment-related HBsAg loss in HBeAg-negative chronic hepatitis B: a clue from serum HBsAg levels. *Antivir Ther* 2007;12(1):73-82.
 27. Hadziyannis SJ, Sevastianos V, Rapti I, Vassilopoulos D, Hadziyannis E. Sustained responses and loss of HBsAg in HBeAg-negative patients with chronic hepatitis B who stop long-term treatment with adefovir. *Gastroenterology* 2012;143(3):629-36 e1. Epub 2012/06/05.
 28. Brunetto MR, Oliveri F, Colombatto P, Moriconi F, Ciccorossi P, Coco B, et al. Hepatitis B surface antigen serum levels help to distinguish active from inactive hepatitis B virus genotype D carriers. *Gastroenterology* 2010;139(2):483-90.
 29. Chen J, Wang L, Li Y, Cai B, Fu Y, Liao Y, et al. Association analysis between SNPs in IL-28B gene and the progress of hepatitis B infection in Han Chinese. *PloS One* 2012;7(12):e50787.
 30. Chen J, Wang W, Li X, Xu J. A meta-analysis of the association between IL28B polymorphisms and infection susceptibility of hepatitis B virus in Asian population. *BMC Gastroenterology* 2015 12;15:58.
 31. Ren S, Lu J, Du X, Huang Y, Ma L, Huo H, et al. Genetic variation in IL28B is associated with the development of hepatitis B-related hepatocellular carcinoma. *Cancer Immunol Immunother* 2012;61(9):1433-9.
 32. Zhang Y, Zhu SL, Chen J, Li LQ. Meta-analysis of associations of interleukin-28B polymorphisms rs8099917 and rs12979860 with development of hepatitis virus-related hepatocellular carcinoma. *Oncotargets Ther* 2016; 30:3249-57
 33. Xia P, Zhou M, Dong DS, Xing YN, Bai Y. Association of polymorphisms in interleukin-18 and interleukin-28B genes with outcomes of hepatitis B virus infections: a meta-analysis. *Tumour Biol* 2014;35(2):1129-37.
 34. Lee IC, Lin CH, Huang YH, Huo TI, Su CW, Hou MC, et al. IL28B polymorphism correlates with active hepatitis in patients with HBeAg-negative chronic hepatitis B. *PloS One* 2013;8(2):e58071.
 35. Li Y, Shi Y, Chen J, Cai B, Ying B, Wang L. Association of polymorphisms in interleukin-18 and interleukin-28B with hepatitis B recurrence after liver transplantation in Chinese Han population. *Int J Immunogenet* 2012;39(4):346-52.
 36. Hadziyannis E, Laras A, Panopoulou E, Anagnostopoulou S, Hadziyannis SJ. The IL28B polymorphism does not correlate with treatment-induced and spontaneous outcomes in chronic hepatitis B. *Hepatology* 2013;58S:633A.
 37. Domagalski K, Pawłowska M, Zaleśna A, Tyczyno M, Skorupa-Kłaput M, Tretyn A, et al. The relationship between IL-28B polymorphisms and the response to peginterferon alfa-2a monotherapy in anti-HBe-positive patients with chronic HBV infection. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis* 2014;33(11):2025-33
 38. Manesis EK, Hadziyannis SJ. Interferon alpha treatment and retreatment of hepatitis B e antigen-negative chronic hepatitis B. *Gastroenterology* 2001;121(1):101-9.

